

Cities in shape: the effect of urban morphology on sustainable mobility accessibility to urban amenities

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Summary

Sustainable mobility has become one of the grand challenges of the 21st Century. Multiple cities in the world have acknowledged this fact, and are promoting more sustainable mobility habits among their citizens. However, these policies must be linked to a built environment that favours such behaviours. This project aims at studying how the urban form, land use, and the socioeconomic characteristics of local areas affect accessibility to urban amenities in a set of international case studies. This abstract presents the author's PhD project, to be developed over the next three years and intended at providing a holistic view on local accessibility in cities.

KEYWORDS: 15-minute city, urban morphology, urban morphometrics, sustainable mobility, accessibility.

1 Introduction

Sustainable mobility has become one of the grand challenges of the 21st Century. The increasing evidence of the noxious effects of urban air pollution and its relation to motorised traffic has contributed to the development of new policies aimed at promoting clean modes of mobility (Khomeenko et al., 2021; Sicard et al., 2020). In Paris, the '15-minute city' envisions a city where basic amenities can be reached within a 15 minute walking or cycling radius (Moreno et al., 2021). Similarly, Copenhagen has focused on transit-oriented development policies which promote compact and dense residential areas built close to public transport stations (Curtis et al., 2009). At the heart of these policies lays the need to align sustainable mobility policies with providing a built environment that favours these behaviours.

A key component of this new wave of policies is local accessibility. The focus on locality has become increasingly palpable in the later years, as the neighbourhood has gained importance as analysis unit (Pozoukidou and Chatziyiannaki, 2021). Counting on a solid and varied network of amenities within short-time travel distances has proven key for granting sustainable urban mobility (Elldér et al.,

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2022), and has become a very relevant issue for many citizens following the COVID-19 pandemic (Córdoba-Hernández et al., 2020; Maestosi et al., 2021).

Urban form and urban design play a key role in granting accessibility. A recent report published by the Centre for Cities (Rodrigues and Breach, 2021) addressed the need to grant access to public transport networks in British cities. One of the conclusions of the report is the importance of pairing the expansion of public transport networks with building denser, higher-rise housing developments. This aligns with other studies that assessed which built-environment qualities are related with better accessibility (Ewing and Handy, 2009; Harvey et al., 2016). These studies are based on the measurement of the urban form, a discipline that has recently gained momentum with the development of urban morphometrics subfield, that aims at quantifying the elements of the built environment using geocomputation techniques (Fleischmann et al., 2021, 2020).

The conjunction of a newfound interest on local accessibility, the increased awareness of the effects of the built environment on sustainable mobility, and the development of new urban morphology quantification techniques, allows for the exploration of novel and exciting research paths. This abstract presents the author’s PhD project, which aims at providing a holistic view of local accessibility. This research will bring together elements from GIS and geocomputation, urban morphology, geodemographics and urban economics, and will pay special attention to how the urban form affects the way we relate to our cities and their effect on sustainable mobility choices. The final goal is to provide policy-makers and urban planners with evidence on what urban models are more suitable for promoting sustainable mobility amongst all citizens.

2 Methods and data

2.1 Methods

First, this project will perform an accessibility to urban amenities analysis across cities in Europe and North America. Case study selection will be data-driven, and amenities to be included in the study will be based on existing time use and travel purpose surveys (i.e. Department for Transport (2021)). This will allow for allocating different weights to amenities based on their relevance across different population groups. Different techniques (i.e. isochrones, street network distances) will be tested to calculate accessibility to selected amenities (Balletto et al., 2021; Calafiore et al., 2022). Parameters such as speed or preferred routes will be tuned to accommodate the needs of different population groups (i.e. children, the elderly). Based on the number and variety of available amenities, accessibility scores will be assigned to different areas in the city.

The next step aims at characterising both the physical, functional and socioeconomic elements of the selected case studies. First, a morphometric analysis will allow for quantifying and measuring which elements of the urban form (e.g. street network, plots, and buildings) favour accessibility. To do this, Fleischmann (2019)’s *momepy* package will be used. Land use analysis will help determine which combinations of urban activities relate to higher accessibility. Finally, the socioeconomic characteristics of the different areas and their inhabitants will also be studied.

2.2 Data and software

This project aims to use open-source data and software. Data on urban amenities and morphology will be downloaded from OpenStreetMap (OSM) (OpenStreetMap Contributors, 2017). Socioeconomic indicators will be obtained from country and city-level statistics databases. The decision on which cities to include in the case studies will be driven by the existence of such databases with comparable information. It is acknowledged that this poses a limitation to the geographical scope of this research, as many cities around the world do not have the resources to set up and maintain their own Statistics departments. Analyses will be conducted using free software tools such as (RStudio Team, 2020), Python (Python Software Foundation, 2021), and QGIS (QGIS Development Team, 2021).

3 Project Timeline

This project will run over the next three years. The first 18 months will be focused on the accessibility and morphometric analyses. The following 12 months will be dedicated to the socioeconomic analysis, and to the development of interactive tools that allow for the visualisation of the analysis results.

4 Acknowledgements

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5 Biography

Clara is a PhD student at the Geospatial Systems CDT, a partnership between Newcastle University and the University of Nottingham. Her background is in Applied Economics, and her research interests lie in the areas of urban studies and sustainable mobility. Prior to joining the CDT, she worked as a research assistant at City, University of London (UK), and IESE Business School (Spain).

References

- Balletto, G., Ladu, M., Milesi, A., and Borruso, G. (2021). A methodological approach on disused public properties in the 15-minute city perspective. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(2):1–19.
- Calafiore, A., Dunning, R., Nurse, A., and Singleton, A. (2022). The 20-minute city: An equity analysis of Liverpool City Region. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, 102:103111.
- Córdoba-Hernández, R., Fernández-Ramírez, C., Hernández-Aja, A., Salgado, G. S. T., and Gómez-Giménez, J. M. (2020). Urban areas in front of neighborhoods. Analysis of urban characteristics in the face of the challenge of the post-COVID 19 city: The case of Madrid. *Ciudad y Territorio Estudios Territoriales*, 52(205):665–684.

- Curtis, C., Renne, J. L., and Bertolini, L. (2009). *Transit oriented development: making it happen*. Ashgate Publishing, Ltd.
- Department for Transport (2021). National Travel Survey. Available via: <https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/national-travel-survey-statistics>.
- Elldér, E., Haugen, K., and Vilhelmson, B. (2022). When local access matters: A detailed analysis of place, neighbourhood amenities and travel choice. *Urban Studies*, 59(1):120–139.
- Ewing, R. and Handy, S. (2009). Measuring the Unmeasurable: Urban Design Qualities Related to Walkability. *Journal of Urban Design*, 14(1):65–84.
- Fleischmann, M. (2019). momepy: Urban Morphology Measuring Toolkit. *Journal of Open Source Software*, 4(43):1807.
- Fleischmann, M., Feliciotti, A., and Kerr, W. (2021). Evolution of Urban Patterns: Urban Morphology as an Open Reproducible Data Science. In *Geographical Analysis*. Blackwell Publishing Inc.
- Fleischmann, M., Romice, O., and Porta, S. (2020). Measuring urban form: Overcoming terminological inconsistencies for a quantitative and comprehensive morphologic analysis of cities. *Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science*.
- Harvey, C., Aultman-Hall, L., Troy, A., and Hurley, S. E. (2016). Streetscape skeleton measurement and classification. *Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science*, 44(4):668–692.
- Khomenko, S., Cirach, M., Pereira-Barboza, E., Mueller, N., Barrera-Gómez, J., Rojas-Rueda, D., de Hoogh, K., Hoek, G., and Nieuwenhuijsen, M. (2021). Premature mortality due to air pollution in European cities: a health impact assessment. *The Lancet Planetary Health*, 5(3):e121–e134.
- Maestosi, P. C., Andreucci, M. B., and Civiero, P. (2021). Sustainable urban areas for 2030 in a post-covid-19 scenario: Focus on innovative research and funding frameworks to boost transition towards 100 positive energy districts and 100 climate-neutral cities. *Energies*, 14(1).
- Moreno, C., Allam, Z., Chabaud, D., Gall, C., and Pratlong, F. (2021). Introducing the “15-Minute City”: Sustainability, Resilience and Place Identity in Future Post-Pandemic Cities. *Smart Cities*, 4(1):93–111.
- OpenStreetMap Contributors (2017). Planet dump retrieved from <https://planet.osm.org>. Available via: <https://www.openstreetmap.org>.
- Pozoukidou, G. and Chatziyiannaki, Z. (2021). 15-minute city: Decomposing the new urban planning Eutopia. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(2):1–25.
- Python Software Foundation (2021). Python Language Reference, version 3.9. Available via: <http://www.python.org>.
- QGIS Development Team (2021). QGIS Geographic Information System. Available via: <http://qgis.osgeo.org>.

Rodrigues, G. and Breach, A. (2021). Measuring up Comparing public transport in the UK and Europe's biggest cities. Technical report, Centre for Cities.

RStudio Team (2020). RStudio: Integrated Development for R. Available via: <http://www.rstudio.com>.

Sicard, P., De Marco, A., Agathokleous, E., Feng, Z., Xu, X., Paoletti, E., Rodriguez, J. J. D., and Calatayud, V. (2020). Amplified ozone pollution in cities during the COVID-19 lockdown. *Science of the Total Environment*, 735.